

TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS TO THE STUDENTS IN THE ENGLISH LESSONS

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ANNOTATION: This article is about learning English, speaking skills, teaching methods and some difficulties in teaching students to speak.

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To date, teaching speaking skills is one of the most important aspects of teaching English, since the main purpose of learning a language is the ability to speak this language well.

Communicative knowledge of a foreign language, providing oral and written information, understanding of what is heard or read, translation is possible only with a certain level of skills, namely, with automated mastery of language material. Therefore, the central task of the educational process in English classes is the formation of such skills that would provide university graduates with the practical application of a foreign language within the limits provided for by the learning objectives.

The leading component in the content of the process of learning a foreign language is a skill. Optimal conditions for the formation of skills and complex skills can be provided by such a structure of the educational process, which will allow to distribute in any given proportion the total study time between exercises that form skills and complex skills provided for by the purpose of training: to provide effective feedback and correction in the learning process.

The skill is formed as a result of repeated repetition of certain actions and it

is impossible to judge the course of its formation based on the results of one exercise. To assess the skill level, you need to analyze the data on the performance of a series of exercises. Therefore, feedback is the most important for the process of learning a foreign language. Thus, in order to create optimal conditions for the formation of skills, the structure of the educational process should provide the possibility of feedback "at the highest level", as well as the possibility of correction based on the data of this connection. The process of formation of skills in different categories of trainees occurs differently. For those who are more malleable to training, this process goes faster, for those who are less malleable, it is associated with a number of additional difficulties and proceeds more slowly.

One of the goals of teaching students of higher educational institutions a foreign language is to develop their conversation skills. Therefore, from the very first year, students need to be taught the skills of perceiving foreign speech and memorizing a short message in a foreign language. The program of the 1st course on the textbook "The business" provides for the study of business vocabulary, business texts, as well as a number of exercises related to the topic to consolidate students with the material they have passed. In addition, already in the 1st year, students need to develop those skills that should then form the basis of work on developing their conversation skills. Practicing vocabulary, and this or that grammatical exercise, we build the lesson so that it contains elements of question-and-answer work, the ability to engage in communication, develop students' attention, memory, skills of quick and correct perception of foreign speech by ear. For example, when studying the topic "Fundamentals of Business", you should pay attention to phrases, since not knowing phrases leads to ignorance of the correct use of certain words in speech.

Experience has shown that students perceive and remember abbreviations, as well as complex words, especially poorly, and make a large number of

mistakes when translating them by ear. Therefore, starting from the 1st course, it is necessary to conduct as many oral training exercises as possible. Such errors as 15(fifteen) - (five), 12 (twelve) - (twenty).

Learning a foreign language in the 1st year should not be a simple repetition of the basics received by students in high school, it should contain completely new types of work that contribute to achieving the ultimate goals of studying in higher educational institutions.

The methods that develop speaking skills include:

1. *Role-playing game*. For example, when studying a topic (profession), the teacher divides students into groups and gives them roles such as doctor, teacher, hairdresser, pilot, etc. This contributes to the expression of their thoughts in English, as students present themselves in one role or another.
2. *Brainstorming*. For a limited time, students express their opinions quickly and easily on any topic. A good feature of this method is that students share their ideas without thinking.
3. *Storytelling*. This method helps to consolidate the new vocabulary of the previous lessons. For example, the first student says a sentence, then along the chain the others add one word by meaning, etc.
4. *Cluster (Spider)*. The teacher writes a word from the topics covered on the blackboard. For example, class (class). The word is written in a circle in the form of a "sun". Students can be divided into groups at the discretion of the teacher. They go to the blackboard one by one and write down the words. After all the words are written down, a question is asked. What objects are in the class? This method develops not only speaking skills, but also writing.
5. *Description of the picture*. Students are divided into groups. Each group describes its own picture. At the same time, students try to speak using their vocabulary. They often make grammatical mistakes, but the most important thing is that they speak.

Thus, learning to speak when learning a foreign language is very important. No matter what method the teacher uses, it is important that he first of all motivates students, develops their interest in the subject being studied, educates them in love for the motherland and invests their soul!

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